

RHEOCHOR AND ITS APPLICATION

By W. V. BHAGWAT, P. M. TOSHNIWAL AND V. A. MOGHE

The suggestion of Newton Friend to use viscosity for finding rheochors has been investigated and atomic rheochors calculated. It is shown that the values give fairly accurate results with rheochors of substances obtained experimentally. The suggestion has been extended to solutions and shown to be applicable to cane sugar solution.

Newton Friend (*Nature*, 1942, 140, 432) suggested that in Sudgen's parachor $\sigma \frac{1}{4}$ may be substituted by $\eta \frac{1}{8}$, where σ and η are surface tension and viscosity respectively of the liquid. This gives

$$\frac{M\eta \frac{1}{8}}{D} = \text{Constant} = R$$

where M is the molecular weight and D , the density of the liquid. The same *Rheochor* is suggested for this constant. Friend observes that isomerides yield identical values of R . However, he has published no data as regards atomic rheochors and their application.

We have tried to use this formula for calculating rheochors of several liquids and thus calculated the values of atomic rheochors. The values of D and η in the following table are obtained from the Chemist's Year Book (1937) and are at 20°.

TABLE I

Liquid,	$\eta \times 100$,	D ,	R ,	Group diff.	Diff. of R .
C_6H_6 ,	0.65	0.879	47.28	} CH_2	7.45
$C_6H_6 \cdot CH_2$,	0.59	0.864	54.73		
$m \cdot C_6H_4(CH_3)_2$	0.61	0.864	64.72	} CH_3	10.0
CH_3OH	0.59	0.790	21.33		
C_2H_5OH	1.19	0.789	33.49	} CH_2	12.16
$(C_2H_5)_2O$	0.23	0.716	49.56		
$(CH_3)_4CO$	0.33	0.732	35.83	} $2(CH_2)$	2(8.035)
CH_3COOH	1.22	1.054	32.82		
$OHCl_3$	0.56	1.488	41.89		
CCl_4	0.97	1.582	54.58		
CS_2	0.37	1.292	29.0		
CO_2 (liquid)	0.07	0.83	21.89		
Br_2	0.99	3.187	13.8		
Hg	1.66	13.59	8.75		
$n \cdot C_6H_{14}$,	0.32	0.660	63.55		
$C_6H_5NH_2$	0.44	1.018	46.36		

Having failed to obtain a constant value for CH_2 group we determined the rheochors of the members of homologous series available in our laboratory. Following are the results.

TABLE II

Liquid.	$\eta \times 100$.	D .	Temp.	R .	Group diff.	R . diff.
Methyl alcohol	... 0.59	0.790	20°	21.38	} CH ₂	} 12.16
Ethyl alcohol	... 1.19	0.789	..	33.49		
	... 1.047	0.785	25°	33.13	} CH ₂	} 12.0
Propyl alcohol	... 1.851	0.8078	..	45.12		
Amyl alcohol	... 2.900	0.8052	..	70.21	} 2 (CH ₂)	} 2 (12.55)
Acetic acid	... 1.22	1.054	20°	32.82		
Butyric acid	... 1.677	0.9528	25°	55.42	} 2 (CH ₂)	} 2 (11.3)
Ethyl formate	... 0.424	0.9099	25°	41.09		
Ethyl acetate	... 0.436	0.888	..	50.21	} CH ₂	} 9.12
Ethyl butyrate	... 0.8033	0.867	..	70.64		
Acetone	... 0.33	0.792	20°	35.83	} 2 (CH ₂)	} 2 (10.21)
Methylethyl ketone	... 0.45	0.805	25°	45.53		
					} CH ₂	} 9.7

The values of CH₂ group for associated liquids as alcohols and acids are somewhat high. Average value of rheochor of CH₂ is 10, and the values of atomic rheochors calculated with this value gives better results than any other value of CH₂ group. Substituting this value for the rheochor of CH₂ in hexane, ethyl ether, and other compounds we get the following values of atomic rheochors.

TABLE III

Element.	R .	Element.	R .
Hydrogen	... 1.77	Chlorine	11.6 (average)
Carbon	... 6.44	Bromine	13.8
Oxygen	... 6.02	Mercury	8.75
Sulphur	... 11.28		

These values of atomic rheochors, when substituted in various compounds, reproduce the rheochors of the compounds fairly accurately although alcohols and aromatic hydrocarbons show marked deviation. In case of alcohols and acids the variation is partly due to the different values of hydroxyl and carboxyl oxygen than the value given in table which is for rheochor of ethereal oxygen and partly, due to the difference in the calculated and observed value for alcohols is not being the same although they contain the same number of atoms of hydroxyl oxygen. Similarly the variation of rheochors of aromatic hydrocarbons from experimental values is not constant although each contain only one benzene ring. It is not possible therefore to calculate rheochor for a ring of six. The variation is also not due to incorrect values of C and H rheochors, for the difference of rheochors from member to member is not very constant and that when the value of CH₂ from alcohols or aromatic hydrocarbons is substituted in other compounds, we get wrong results for rheochors of these compounds. Any how it is not possible to explain the discrepancy at this stage and the

values of atomic rheochor given above have to be taken as fairly accurate. Further work is in progress. The following table gives our results.

TABLE IV

Substance.	<i>R</i>		Substance.	<i>R</i>	
	obs.	calc.		obs.	calc.
<i>n</i> -Hexane	63.55	63.55	Benzene	47.28	49.26
Ethyl ether	49.56	49.57	Toluene	54.73	59.26
Carbon tetrachloride	54.58	53.24	<i>m</i> -Xylene	64.72	69.26
Carbon bisulphide	29.0	29.0	Acetic acid	32.82	32.0
Chloroform	41.89	43.0	Butyric acid	55.42	52.0
Acetone	35.83	36.0	Methyl alcohol	21.33	19.54
Methylethyl ketone	45.53	46.0	Ethyl alcohol	33.13	29.54
Ethyl formate	41.09	42.0	Propyl alcohol	45.12	39.54
Ethyl acetate	50.21	52.0	Amyl alcohol	70.21	59.54
Ethyl butyrate	70.64	72.0	Carbon dioxide		
Water	10.0	9.5	(liquid)	21.89	18.44

We suggest that like parachor, rheochor can be determined by the solution method both from liquids and solids by the expression,

$$R_m = R(1-x) + xR_x$$

where R_m is the rheochor of the solution, R of the solvent and R_x of the solute whose molecular fraction in solution is x . R_m is given by the expression,

$$R_m = \frac{M_m \eta}{D}$$

where M_m = the mean molecular weight of the solution,

η = the viscosity of the solution,

D = the density of the solution.

M_m is obtained from the equation $M = M(1-x) + xM_x$

where M and M_x are the molecular weights of solvent and solute respectively.

Our suggestion is somewhat confirmed in case of cane sugar dissolved in water. The results of η and D in Table V are obtained from Chemist's Year Book, 1937.

TABLE V

R for water = 10.26. Temp. = 20°.

x .	M_m	η .	D .	R_m .	R_x .
0.01299	22.2	2.267	1.083	12.77	204
0.03390	28.99	7.468	1.179	17.78	230

Calculated value for R_x with $\text{CH}_2 = 10$ is 182.5, while with $\text{CH}_2 = 12$ as in alcohols it is approximately 210. If we take $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 10.26$ and $\text{C} = 6.44$, we get $R_x = 190$. It is clear therefore that solution law seems to be applicable. Further work is in progress to get more accurate values of atomic rheochors from various substances.